

Reporting on Reality: The Lived Experiences of Journalists in the Age of Disinformation

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Abstract-

Introduction: Disinformation poses significant challenges for societies, with journalists playing a crucial role in countering its effects by providing objective information to the public.

Methodology: This qualitative study employs phenomenology as its research design to explore the impact of disinformation on journalists in Qatar through semi-structured interviews. Mainly, it aimed to answer the central question "What aspects of life are journalists most affected by disinformation?" and more specifically, the question of "How does disinformation impact the personal and professional lives of journalists?"

Results: From the verbal musings of the participants, three key themes emerged: Journalistic Operation, Journalistic Introspection, and Journalistic Determination.

Discussion: Journalistic Operation encompasses Informative Precision, Dialogue Navigation, and Journalistic Complication, reflecting the processes and challenges journalists face. Journalistic Introspection involves Media Obligation, Ethical Consideration, and Influence Dissection, highlighting journalists' self-reflection on their roles and responsibilities. Journalistic Determination, demonstrated through Positivity Emanation, Boundary Adaptation, and Advocacy Devotion, showcases journalists' resilience and commitment.

Conclusion: The study underscores journalists' complex challenges amid rampant disinformation, emphasizing the importance of upholding their duty to the public. Future researchers could explore the public's media and information literacy and its impact on journalists' adaptation strategies and consider other factors, such as nationality, to reflect disinformation's global and multi-cultural nature.

Index Terms: Disinformation, fake news, journalists, media, adjustments.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of the Internet, it is easier than ever to share information; however, such convenience will also lead to the sharing of false information for malicious purposes, known as disinformation. Disinformation is a form of falsehood with the primary purpose of deceiving people by mimicking real news (Tandoc, 2019). Today, the phenomenon is more contagious than ever, as purported facts deceive many people into disseminating them on social media and other platforms. This snowball effect will lead to many adverse outcomes. In the digital age, the unchecked dissemination of false information has assumed a new form, posing complex problems for democracy (Balod & Hameleers, 2021).

As a result of recent events, the COVID-19 pandemic has amplified a growing trend in disinformation. There have been reports of diverse conspiracies, with the most dangerous ones focusing on vaccines and their supposed harmful effects. There is currently a social media movement working to discredit vaccines and persuade individuals to disregard the vaccination recommendations of governments and health organizations (Herrera-Peco et al., 2021). Aside from the health sector, disinformation is most evident in politics and often seen during elections. It was observed that specific political candidates during the Philippine elections were weaponizing the disinformation campaigns of their supporters to boost their electoral standings (Gianan, 2020). These disinformation campaigns were manufactured purposefully and disseminated, stirring up social unrest and political upheaval and rallying support or discontent for their desired political figure. Disinformation is frequently mixed with news that is only partially true to increase the news's legitimacy. Thus, disinformation can be seen as a rampant and ongoing phenomenon, and its impacts on various sectors of society, from health to politics, are clear.

The impacts of disinformation can also be seen in the profession that aims to deliver the truth to the masses and combat the rampant disinformation in today's discourse—journalism. Due to the benefits of publishing journalistic works online, especially accessibility, news reaches several people on several platforms promptly. However, due to how

debatable online news is, it leaves readers more skeptical about whether or not the content is true or false, despite already proving its credibility. Disinformation is causing significant challenges for journalists, with many news organizations struggling to maintain Trust in the face of online disinformation. It is more effective when it is disseminated by sources perceived as credible and trustworthy, making it even more critical for journalists to maintain their credibility and reputation in the public eye. Journalists must address this issue directly and emphasize the importance of the core principles of their profession, which go beyond just reporting facts correctly and presenting balanced viewpoints. These principles include a commitment to a thorough verification process demonstrating the rigor behind high-quality journalism in an educational setting (Richardson, 2017).

Despite the impacts of disinformation on journalism, there is a lack of comprehensive research that analyzes the impacts of disinformation on the journalists themselves on a micro-level. Some studies may have examined the effects of disinformation on specific aspects of journalism, such as media coverage, news production, and audience perceptions. Existing studies have also investigated the critical actors behind it, how it spreads, and how ordinary people react to disinformation (Hamaleers, 2022; Akers et al., 2018; Ručinská, 2022). However, the research gap about the journalists themselves will inhibit the understanding of a holistic picture of how disinformation impacts the media landscape. The reach of disinformation has consistently been found to be very constrained. In light of this, it can be more challenging to accurately predict the spread of disinformation after it enters closed communication spaces from mostly public platforms (Jungherr & Schroeder, 2021). The spread of disinformation poses a significant threat to societal discourse, and more research is needed to understand the impact of disinformation on the media landscape by examining its impact on journalists. The field of journalism is front and center in countering the threat of disinformation to public discourse, and the lived experiences of those who thoroughly report about the present happenings are significant in today's volatile world of disinformation. As such, the research is aimed at the people who report on reality and are at the forefront of combating disinformation.

In the disinformation age, the journalists' lived experiences offer invaluable insights into the complexities of combating its adverse effects within the media landscape (Seshan, 2016). Through transparent sharing, journalists foster audience trust and underscore their dedication to accuracy, countering the manipulative tactics employed by those in positions of authority. This approach emphasizes the role of journalists' experiences in making information more accessible to a broader audience (Seshan, 2016). Efforts to bridge the gap between professional news and the public are crucial, with a critical examination of disinformation revealing transformative possibilities and addressing power imbalances (Kuo & Marwick, 2021). Collaboration among journalists facilitates the development of practical solutions, which is essential for addressing the historical misuse of news formats for non-journalistic purposes (Ang et al., 2020).

This study aimed to examine Qatar-based journalists with the central question: "What aspects of life do journalists are most affected by disinformation?" and investigate the lives of journalists in the age of disinformation. Following the central question, the specific question: "How does disinformation impact the personal and professional lives of journalists?" is now related to how disinformation has impacted their lives inside and outside their profession. These questions were formulated to narrow the central inquiry and extract more specific responses. The responses will be processed and evaluated to derive the recurring themes found in the simulacrum. Journalists are one of the professions at the forefront of combating disinformation. With their struggles considered, the main objective of this study is to explore and understand the perspectives of the participants who have had to experience their personal and professional lives in this tumultuous age.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study is qualitative in method and categorically a phenomenological research design, as it aims to understand the participants' lived experiences. Qualitative research deals with process, context, interpretation, meaning, or understanding through an inductive approach. Additionally, qualitative research can shed light on how different people and groups view and respond to these changes, which can help to inform a particular and focused strategy to lessen the detrimental effects on society (Gobat et al., 2018; Vindrola-Padros et al., 2020). Meanwhile, a phenomenological research approach was applied in this study, as it is designed to understand the participants' experiences and perceptions regarding the lived experiences of journalists in the age of disinformation. Phenomenology is used for studies focused on understanding the essence of a particular group of people's lived experiences (Tomaszewski, 2020). The issue was not just the foundation upon which human experience depended but also its source in terms of its fundamental nature. Phenomenology also focuses on studying an individual's lived experiences within the world (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Research Locus and Sample

This research was conducted in Qatar, where all participants are journalists. A total of 10 Qatar-based journalists, consisting of five males and five females, were selected as participants in this study. The researchers used a purposeful

sampling strategy to choose the participants. Purposeful sampling was used to recruit the interviewees as this sampling method is ideal in matching the participants to the aims and objectives of the research, thus improving the study's rigor and trustworthiness of the data and results. (Campbell et al., 2017). The participants for this research were selected following the criteria set: (1) is undergoing or has attained at least a bachelor's degree in mass communication or journalism, (2) is working or has worked for a media company as a journalist, (3) has 1-year work experience in the field, and (4) is aged 22 and above. The generated criteria were carefully observed so that their genuine views and perspectives would reflect the journalists' thinking in the disinformation age.

Data Collection and Ethical Consideration

The data-gathering process began with formulating the interview questions based on the central and specific questions. Then, chosen teachers with relevant professional backgrounds validated those questions. Following validation, participants received emails with consent forms inviting them to participate in the study. The participants' availability determined the time and location of the interviews. Then, the Zoom Conference application was used to conduct the interviews.

The interviews were conducted using the robotfoto and interview guide. The participants also received an orientation to give them a run-through of the interview procedure. As for the recording of the interviews, which the participants consented to, the Zoom meeting recording feature was utilized. For transcription purposes, the researcher requested permission to record the meeting. In line with the qualitative research procedure of the study, the researchers utilized the data interpretation and analysis in addition to the transcription of the oral responses. The participants' confidentiality was upheld in the transcription, so their names will not appear; instead, they were referred to as P1, P2, P3, and so on.

Data Analysis

The participants' experiences were directly gathered and used as data in this study. From their responses obtained through the designed interview, the research flow was observed using the following steps in data analysis: (1) Emic data transcription; (2) Emic to Etic transcription; (3) Cool to Warm Analysis; (4) identifying and analyzing themes through the dendrogram tool; and (5) the integration of these themes into the simulacrum of this research. Through this methodical approach, the study analyzed journalists' experiences through thematic analysis, gaining a thorough understanding of the subject. The first data analysis stage clarified the information collected through direct transcriptions and data cleaning. The data treatment follows, with the cool-warm analysis clustered and reflected to form the dendrogram, which then extracts the themes and the sub-themes created. The research's simulacrum embodies the study's conceptual framework and illustrates the relationships between the constituent parts. The second level of data analysis then reinforces the themes and subthemes through the lenses of relevant studies and literature.

III. RESULTS

This phenomenological study explores the experiences of journalists—more specifically, journalists based in Qatar—regarding disinformation. It seeks to comprehend the journalistic experiences and viewpoints regarding the challenges relevant to the central question, "What aspects of life do journalists most affected by disinformation?" Additionally, this study focused on the specific question, "How does disinformation impact the personal and professional lives of journalists?" Disinformation has created a dynamic environment in journalism that has forced journalists to adjust to their new circumstances.

Based on the responses of the Qatar-based journalists, the key to knowing their untold lived experiences relies on the three main themes, namely: (1) Journalistic Operation - the processes involved in the reporting of reality and its means of informing the inner management and the public; (2) Journalistic Introspection - the moral considerations involved with journalism and the inherent knowledge of the journalists' duty to the public and society; (3) Journalistic Determination - the journalists' optimistic navigation through the age of disinformation. With the emergence of these themes and sub-themes, the readers will better understand the difficulties encountered and the adaptation made by different journalists in Qatar in light of the rampant disinformation within society.

Figure 1 shows the simulacrum presenting the three major themes: Journalistic Operation, Journalistic Introspection, and Journalistic Determination. These themes signify the particular life aspects of the journalists' experiences with disinformation, namely, the professional processes and operations, introspective reflections, and devoted Determination. Additionally, different sub-themes were recognized, specifically, Informative Precision, Dialogue Navigation, and Journalistic Complication under Journalistic Operation; Media Obligation, Ethical Consideration, and Influence Dissection under Journalistic Introspection; and Positivity Emanation, Boundary Adaptation, and Advocacy Devotion under Journalistic Determination.

Fig. 1: Impacts of Disinformation on Journalists and Their Adjustments

Journalistic Operation

The first central theme discusses the processes and challenges in journalism. Operation deals with significant operational processes within the journalistic landscape that ensure factual accuracy. Therefore, Journalistic Operation tackles the professional aspect and the journalists' methodology. It focuses on how journalists ensure factual accuracy and the challenges of such a task. Aspects relating to operations such as communication and reporting are substantial for a journalist as these underpin major cornerstones within journalism. Thus, journalists must be able to communicate their thoughts and stresses and report on reality through in-depth research and responsible data-gathering. Three sub-themes emerged from this significant theme: Informative Precision, Dialogue Navigation, and Journalistic Complication.

A. Informative Precision

The very role of a journalist is to communicate events and stories to the public factually and accurately. Fact-checking and being critical are vital cornerstones of this process. Due to disinformation, this process has become more vital than ever, and journalists need to be precise with their information. Two of the participants highlighted:

"As a journalist, if you want to pursue journalism, you have to check and double-check. There is no end to fact-checking." (P1)

"You double-check everything, absolutely everything." (P8)

Another participant seconded this response; however, he/she stated that his/her practice of fact-checking did not entirely depend on his/her profession as a journalist but instead on his/her personality. As stated:

"I feel that to be a reflection of my nature, and although some people are easily convinced, I just make sure to double-check and steer clear of dubious sources of information and other such things. I think my goal has always been to fact-check and double-check, to ensure that the sources are accurate, especially before I became a journalist." (P4)

Supporting this notion, another participant connected his/her experience with the context of the emergence of artificial intelligence in digital journalism. Although artificial intelligence can be a tool to amplify further and disseminate information, it can also be used to fabricate materials and passed off as factual information:

"It is always fact-checking. You can verify if a specific photo is accurate or if it is just artificial intelligence. So we must be vigilant, and hopefully technology can spread this information." (P2)

Moreover, authenticating the source of information and providing the necessary materials and references are crucial in delivering precise information to the public. Every article or news story must have materials and references to back its veracity. Additionally, consulting with people who have a deep background in the topic or were first-hand witnesses to the event is a must for journalists to deliver balanced and accurate news. Two participants underscored:

"You should always research the background among the sources, research their previous works, and always do so because they may be saying something that may be propaganda." (P2)

"First, check the supporting documents or materials. Second, relate a person or people who have massive amounts of information or are very knowledgeable about the subject of the article." (P7)

Sometimes, however, journalists heavily rely on public relations officers and personnel from the concerned organizations and institutions for their press releases and statements as the basis for their reports. Unfortunately, these

personnel and officers can be a source of false information due to miscommunication. Training them to disseminate information better is vital to ensuring precise information is delivered to the journalists for further circulation to the public, as highlighted by a participant:

"...public relations officials need training to ensure accurate information dissemination." (P2)

Another cornerstone of precise reporting is in-depth research on the key elements and details of the event. With the spread of incorrect information, this step is significant in ensuring that all the information is factual, as discussed by two participants:

"You seek the truth. When you are researching or writing as a journalist, you focus on the "where," "who," and "why," along with the "how" and other crucial details. These elements constitute the facts." (P5)

"I exercise patience and conduct thorough research and evaluate the credibility of the sources." (P6)

Thus, achieving informative precision requires an intensive approach that starts from gathering the necessary information and materials and scrutinizing it through endless fact-checking and research. Ultimately, these processes underscore the importance and challenge of journalism in disseminating factual and balanced information to the population so that the broader society can make a sound judgment or form an informed opinion on an issue.

B. Dialogue Navigation

Pertinent to ensuring precise communication of information, communication with people is critical to ensuring factual work. Relations with others, such as their family and colleagues, are significant in the journalists' lives. They communicate and inform their family of developments and issues within their jobs, such as the dangers of disinformation, as demonstrated by a participant:

"I talk to my children about disinformation. I asked her where she found that information, and she often mentioned YouTube. I tell her to be careful about which YouTubers she follows and to fact-check the content she consumes." (P1)

Journalists also talk with their families about their concerns and issues. This conversation is seen as a way to release their stresses emotionally and feel lighter despite the troubles at work. Two participants echoed this sentiment:

"They are my support network." (P2)

"I will share my concerns with my family members. It is always nice to share with others, actually with everyone, because sometimes if you feel much pressure, you have to get it off your chest." (P10)

On the contrary, two participants expressed their desire to keep family out of their career matters. The participants cited that they do not want their family to experience unnecessary stress, and they do not want to raise concerns about their work:

"They have their worries to contend with. I believe in not burdening them with additional concerns." (P3)

"I prefer to shield them from the challenges of my work." (P5)

Communication and work relations with their colleagues were also crucial in their journalistic processes. Disinformation often becomes a galvanizing force that makes journalists form new connections to combat it, as elaborated on by four participants:

"Combating disinformation has facilitated the formation of new connections. These connections, in turn, can assist in the process of verifying the accuracy of the information in question." (P3)

"Well, we [other colleagues] do share information casually, like, 'Did you verify this? Is this factual?' It is not something deliberate; it is just a natural part of our conversations." (P5)

"I would say that combating disinformation has facilitated the formation of new connections within my professional circle." (P6)

"I have one colleague with whom I can discuss all these things regarding disinformation." (P7)

Another dimension in this sub-theme is navigating through differing opinions and beliefs. Especially with the rampant spread of incorrect information, as stated by a participant:

"Especially now with the ongoing war... There are a lot of varying opinions and beliefs. It is a political and religious war, so there is much disinformation." (P2)

Often, disinformation can be a source of contention in friendships. This contention caused by the false information circulated was the basis for personal beliefs. There will be disagreements between an informed opinion and an uninformed belief. Journalists are quick to navigate through this contention by respecting their beliefs; however, they do set boundaries on how much they can tolerate their beliefs, as underscored by a participant:

"I would not sever a friendship over such differences, as beliefs are a personal choice. I would be inclined to distance myself from anyone whose beliefs are fundamentally inhumane or intolerant." (P3)

Journalists frequently navigate a complex web of communication with their families and colleagues. Some journalists air their concerns and stresses to their families, while others want to shield their families from their stresses. Additionally, journalists muse with their fellow journalists about fighting disinformation and staying faithful to their journalistic duty. Moreover, journalists must face the dilemma of knowing which opinion or belief to respect based on their moral principles. This has indicated a communicative adjustment where journalists must be careful and thoughtful

in their conversations. Disinformation has influenced this activity because false information can be the basis of personal beliefs, which causes dissension. Journalists communicate their thoughts to others to enhance their social and professional lives.

C. *Journalistic Complication*

Journalists face multiple challenges throughout their professional lives. They often get burnt out and become stressed due to their workload and other work-related factors, further amplified by disinformation that seeks to endanger their work. Two participants replied:

"Many journalists are burned out." (P2)

"I have contemplated the challenges of this profession." (P6)

The field has become more challenging due to the vast amount of information available. In the age of disinformation, false information can often be indistinguishable from factual information without proper research and verification. Thus, journalists' job of disseminating correct information to the general population becomes harder.

"Yes, being a journalist has indeed become more challenging. It is harder in this age because there is an abundance of information available." (P5)

Inevitably, journalists are forced to step back to recover from this bombardment of information. They find ways to recollect their thoughts and processes and proceed back again to their work with a refreshed mind and outlook, as elucidated by two participants:

"However, in my opinion, the best course of action when handling this knowledge is to sit back, take a deep breath, and once more consider the wider picture." (P4)

"...if you know you are being fed too much information, you must step back." (P9)

These challenges are not only resolved by critical thinking and systematic processes but also with a great deal of intuition and Trust that comes from years of experience on the job, as illustrated by two participants:

"To cope, it is essential to stand by one's work, believe in it, and resonate with it. Facing public opposition becomes more manageable when there is a genuine trust in the work produced." (P6)

"But being a journalist, you have to fight for the truth...you have this gut that you know what is going on." (P9)

Thus, journalism is a dynamic and complex field in which challenges require thoughtful and nuanced solutions. While the issue of professional burnout remains a significant concern for journalists, the need to combat disinformation has become a unifying force, reigniting their commitment to the vital task of informing the public. While recognizing the importance of occasional rest, it is equally crucial to acknowledge journalists' inherent responsibility in leading the fight against fake news. This dedication, rooted in the principles of truth and accuracy, not only emphasizes the importance of their profession but also highlights the essential role journalists play in fostering an informed and resilient society. As they navigate the intricate landscape of disseminating information, journalists continue to be the guardians of truth, unwavering in their dedication to upholding the integrity of the media.

Exploring *Journalistic Operation* has unveiled journalism's intricate processes and challenges. Within its three illuminating sub-themes – Informative Precision, Dialogue Navigation, and Journalistic Complication – a comprehensive understanding of the journalist's professional landscape emerges. Amid the complexity of disinformation, Informative Precision emphasizes the vital role journalists play in providing accurate information. Journalists working together to disseminate information highlight the importance of communication in both personal and professional contexts in Dialogue Navigation. Finally, Journalistic Complication illuminates journalists' difficulties, stressing the importance of experience and intuition in negotiating the ever-changing media environment. Journalists' unwavering commitment to preserving truth and integrity is demonstrated by their struggles with burnout and the deluge of information. As the truth's unshakable defenders in this dynamic age, journalists work hard to spread accurate and trustworthy information, building an informed and resilient society.

Journalistic Introspection

There are three components to a journalist's process, from gathering to reporting information. The second central theme compiles the journalist's obligation to their job, morals, and influence. While *Introspection* defines the observation of one's mental and emotional processes, *journalist introspection* covers journalists' claims of accomplishing their goals and revealing the truth against the disinformation shared. This theme also pertains to the internal mechanisms of journalists in dealing with their jobs and responsibilities. From this, three subthemes emerged: media obligation, ethical consideration, and influence dissection.

A. *Media Obligation*

Journalists are obliged to society to write and report news factually and accurately. This obligation stems from their professional requirements and the public's need for information as a basis for action. Therefore, the journalists' primary

responsibility is to report the truth and disseminate this information to the public for their awareness. Three of the participants verbalized:

"...As a journalist, you present the current situation to the public because you want them to be informed that these things happen." ^(P9)

"As a journalist, your primary responsibility is to report the truth." ^(P5)

"...whatever we present, it is always about giving the right, accurate information..." ^(P10)

Thus, when presented with doubtful information, journalists can remove it from their articles to align with their obligation to the media and the public. This discretion sets compelling journalism apart from blind journalism, where journalists include certain information without confirming its veracity. A participant highlighted this discretion:

"However, you always retain the option not to publish if you have doubts about the veracity of the information or if you do not believe in it." ^(P3)

This responsibility is coupled with the journalists' mindset to work their best for every story so that they can trust the work they have produced. These responses have revealed that the following integrity is a crucial value to have in the field, as verbalized by one of the participants:

"You must always work with integrity. Just give your 100% for every story that you are assigned to." ^(P2)

With that trust, journalists gain the confidence needed to face public scrutiny regarding their work, as highlighted by one of the participants:

"Facing public opposition becomes more manageable when there is a genuine trust in the work produced." ^(P6)

The media obligation for journalists is to always report on happenings. However, it is anyone's media obligation to have a say in any event, giving room for disinformation. As mentioned by the interviewed journalists, their obligations regarding reporting are to update the public on current events and tell them truthfully. With this obligation, they have been given the discretion to omit information they or their editors believe is false. Additionally, as one of the journalists expressed, reports are given to journalists' entire efforts to ensure that the public receives the media due to their concerns of knowing what is happening and how to deal with it, provided the supporting details in the news.

B. Ethical Consideration

Ethics in journalism is founded on journalists' accuracy, objectivity, impartiality, and truthfulness. News reports are written with those ethics to ensure the public can discern the information independently. Hence, the news remains neutral or balanced so readers can decide and debate what should have happened and what should have been done. One of the participants mentioned:

"As a journalist, you strive to source information from multiple credible outlets and individuals when crafting stories. By doing so, you provide readers with a transparent view of the sources of your information, indicating that you are not fabricating the narrative." ^(P9)

Another participant seconded this notion, highlighting that fabricating the narrative to attract readers is unethical in journalism. Readers must have a balanced and objective view of the event at hand so they can make their own decisions. Sensationalist news often skews the narrative towards a particular perspective that influences the reader.

"You just have to be specific. Usually, I would highlight; I would focus on the news first, not on the headlines, clickbait, or the help of sensationalism. I would focus on how much the public wants to hear." ^(P2)

Ethical considerations come into play in the writing process, such as disregarding journalists' bias. It is common practice to refrain from writing their opinions so readers can comment on the news. Journalists should not insert themselves into their news as their personal beliefs and opinions will interfere with the objective nature of the news. One of the participants replied:

"Yes, I think it is better not to take it personally." ^(P8)

Another view is that objective journalism comes from the writing style. Journalists have to write their news reports and articles in a way that a vast majority of the public will understand the news. In essence, writing is critical in delivering information to the masses. When the report is simple, there will be no room for fabrication since the journalists present the facts alone. Wrapping journalistic works in hifalutin words only causes confusion among the readers and, thus, leads readers to act on misinterpreted information. A participant backed this notion:

"I consider my writing style to be quite simple. You must write for readers in simple language." ^(P4)

However, this view is seen as idealistic to other journalists as it is human nature to infuse their sentiments into their work through various stylistic choices. This reveals that, despite the various processes ensuring objectivity, journalistic works have subtle expressions of opinions and values from their writer, as revealed by one of the participants:

"Objective writing, in essence, may not be entirely attainable, as writers inevitably infuse their values, sentiments, and emotions into their work through the selection of words, metaphors, and stylistic choices." ^(P6)

In this disinformation age, journalists are more motivated than ever to evaluate their works' ethical standards and practices. Disinformation, therefore, has catalyzed journalists to remain on reporting the truth, as one participant has mentioned:

"I think this disinformation could motivate people to become journalists because they would be driven by the desire to reveal the truth." ^(P5)

To conclude, it is noticeably vocalized that a journalist's ethics align with the ethical considerations taken in publishing stories. This is seen in the fact that, despite the majority agreement of keeping the work impartial, there is only one opposition that states that, in some less-than-ideal works, there is a bit of a biased opinion. These works do not align with the ethical considerations of journalism, seeing as they spread disinformation with rumors and partiality, completely negating the objectivity of delivering a story. However, not all information shared tries to get the public to believe in one takeaway that ignores the space for debate. A journalist supports this by stating that their project should not be taken personally but professionally.

C. Influence Dissection

Undoubtedly, whatever is written as news will influence its readers. Nevertheless, simply stating that news 'influences' disregards the more profound effects of the change people can experience after reading or hearing a report. Journalists, who are obligated to report the truth, must remember that they serve the broader society. Whatever they put on the newspaper, regardless of whether it is noticeable or not, is sure to affect readers in some way or another. A participant acknowledged that:

"We should give the proper information, the correct information, because it affects people." ^(P7)

However, in this age of accessible information, their influence is being challenged by individuals on the Internet. This indicates that individuals are more empowered than ever in this age. However, this influence has been misused by individuals through spreading disinformation. Two of the participants have mentioned this notion in their replies:

"Everyone has an idea and has a say about something on some issue." ^(P9)

"The 'global village' is the notion of individuals being connected through the Internet and similar things." ^(P4)

Journalists influence the public to act on that particular event or social phenomenon by disseminating the necessary information needed for the public to make an informed decision. In the age of the Internet and other convenient means of disseminating information, this influence is a powerful tool for bad actors to shape public opinion by using false information to further their agendas. Two participants underscore this motive in disinformation:

"Disinformation usually arises from individuals who share or manipulate information with the intent of advancing their interests." ^(P2)

"It is quite simple. People want to shape public opinion. Yeah. That is what it is. Like whoever it is, wherever it is, the reason why they want to disinform is because they are trying to reach a specific strategic outcome." ^(P8)

Despite journalists being the source of information for many people worldwide, they still encourage their readers to fact-check their details and be investigative in the quest for truth. Epistemologically, journalists cannot guarantee that they are delivering the absolute truth. However, their role is to provide factual information and details so that the public can act on such information to uncover the truth and promote a resolution.

"But generally, what is published in newspapers or other media outlets is the information they want you to know. To uncover the truth, you often need to embark on an investigative mission." ^(P3)

Influence is a natural consequence of human interaction today. Even if the entire globe talked about one major event, not everyone on Earth would agree to one singular comment because how the news is written will always leave room for interpretation. The interpretation spreads and changes with each person who consumes media; not every influential intent is received the same way per individual. While journalism impacts the public by providing them with new insight, disinformation impacts the public by manipulating these insights maliciously to get the public to agree with them.

In summary, journalistic Introspection closely analyzes journalists' roles, ethical issues that arise, and how their actions are influenced. The media must highlight the journalist's need to present truthful and correct information for public awareness. To handle public criticism and uphold journalistic norms, integrity and Trust are crucial for journalists. The significance of accuracy, objectivity, and truthfulness is emphasized by ethical consideration, as journalists work to give a fair and impartial perspective while avoiding personal prejudice. Although objective writing is idealized, human nature allows opinions and ideals to be subtly included in journalistic writing. Influence dissection recognizes that news significantly impacts readers, and journalists know how information may sway public opinion. Disinformation is dangerous because dishonest people distort the truth to suit their agendas and sway public opinion. Journalists urge readers to research to find the truth and double-check information. Different viewpoints and interpretations are inevitable, emphasizing how complicated influence is in a world where media is everywhere. Thus, to effectively traverse the dynamic world of journalism and counteract the problems presented by disinformation, journalistic Introspection requires striking a balance between media obligation, ethical considerations, and nuanced knowledge of influence.

Journalistic Determination

The last major theme deals with journalists' optimism, adaptation, and advocacy in the age of disinformation. *Determination* pertains to the dedicated pursuit of truth and fulfilling their obligation while demystifying the profession

and finding ways to involve the public. Thus, this theme talks about their hope for the future of the field, together with navigating their circumstances and staying devoted to their advocacy as journalists.

A. Positivity Emanation

Journalists display a resilient and optimistic outlook toward their profession in the face of rampant disinformation. Despite the evolving landscape, their perspective reflects a collective belief in the enduring importance of journalism and a commitment to upholding its core values. Three participants displayed this optimism by replying:

"It is not about it being taken seriously or not; I believe journalism as a practice will go on. Simply put, the practice's medium will shift." ^(P4)

"I think journalism will take different forms. I do not think it will be taken less seriously; I mean, it is crucial." ^(P8)

This optimistic view is shared by two other participants who emphasized the role of a more critical and empowered youth to practice journalism and uphold its values of objectivity and truthfulness:

"I am an optimist, and it gives me hope when I see young people who care about being factual, truthful, and accurate." ^(P1)

"...if you want journalism by heart, then you will be encouraged to pursue it." ^(P2)

However, not all journalists display this level of optimism towards the future landscape of their profession. Disinformation was cited as a significant factor in their pessimistic outlook on their profession. Two participants verbalized their fears:

"Disinformation might discourage certain individuals. The presence of disinformation may compromise the fundamental purpose of journalism." ^(P3)

"I believe disinformation can discourage individuals from pursuing a career in journalism. When the profession is devalued due to widespread misinformation, it may lead to a lack of credibility and negative connotations." ^(P6)

While these journalists believe that journalism will be compromised in the future by the rampant spread of false information, other journalists perceived disinformation as a motivation to pursue journalism because it is considered a just cause to take up for public welfare and awareness:

"I believe that people are ultimately motivated by the dissemination of misinformation rather than necessarily discouraged by it." ^(P4)

"I think disinformation could motivate people to become journalists because they would be driven by the desire to reveal the truth." ^(P5)

"I think it is more of a motivation because you can combat it." ^(P9)

Such motivation to continue combating disinformation for the betterment of society is also fueled by the journalist's passion combined with their profession:

"I consider my moral convictions about wanting to put out knowledge, better information, inform people, and teach people." ^(P4)

Although there is a level of pessimism from certain journalists, journalists maintain a positive outlook on their profession to continue their work. Disinformation works to delegitimize journalistic works and journalists themselves, so it is paramount that journalists remain steadfast in their pursuits to remain legitimate in the public consciousness.

B. Boundary Adaptation

Adapting to diverse perspectives without fostering animosity emerges as a vital skill. This concept encapsulates journalists' adeptness in maintaining professionalism, employing diplomatic approaches, and seamlessly adapting when confronted with varying opinions. An integral aspect of these journalists is flexibly navigating interactions, fostering a harmonious and constructive journalistic environment, as highlighted by three of the participants:

"I would just choose to be more diplomatic about it. I would be sure to express my opinion, to express my conviction." ^(P2)

"I believe one has to maintain a diplomatic approach in various situations... I suppose it is safe to say I have leaned towards being diplomatic." ^(P5)

"I hold them, and they are open for scrutiny, and I check them, and maybe they change a bit, maybe they do not." ^(P8)

Nevertheless, the ability to be impartial does not come with entering the field, as it is human nature to have bias. Journalists learn how to view the different perspectives of others without malice, which allows them to see the bigger picture of the story and give more information to the audience. This inevitability means that this practice involves putting oneself in an environment that engages with the story and voices one's differences on specific events to truly understand how to get the truth from all the different opinions. These journalists highlight the importance of interaction by stating:

"Attending lectures and engaging with people allows me to understand different viewpoints and strategies in tackling disinformation." ^(P6)

"... I would write about it, and in order to write about it, I would have to talk to people who were involved and affected by it." ^(P8)

Journalists must be bold in stepping up and communicating with their colleagues about their work. Specifically, they are fearless in pointing out errors and lapses in judgment on their colleagues' end. In doing so, they amplify their organization's credibility and accountability, as well as their awareness of potential errors:

"I hold them, and they are open for scrutiny, and I check them, and maybe they change a bit, maybe they do not." ^(P8)
"... I know and inform others that this is wrong." ^(P9)

Thus, journalists' boundaries and acceptance of differing viewpoints are crucial in maintaining workplace consciousness and readiness to face disinformation. Holding their colleagues accountable for their actions signals that they are adept at spotting errors. In this sense, not only are their boundaries being adapted, but the entire ethos of the media organization is also adapted to meet the demands of a democratic society and an empowered newsroom.

C. *Advocacy Devotion*

A compelling dedication to advocacy emerges, transcending the challenges posed by disinformation. Journalists display this unwavering commitment by navigating the complexities of misinformation, actively fostering public awareness, and championing the profound impact of accurate information on society. One of the participants encouraged these actions:

"Keep spreading correct information, and do not let it stop." ^(P1)

It is a grueling task that risks stress for the journalist, but the truth cannot be buried. Despite disinformation, some journalists express being given the motivation to report and educate the masses on the truth. As one of them expressed:

"We must confront false and misleading information to the public and accept responsibility for moving it forward." ^(P10)

Journalists remain steadfast and sincere about their advocacy and fulfilling their obligations within their circle. They are constantly reminding themselves and others of their very purpose as journalists and that they should not stray away from this duty to deliver reliable and balanced information for the public, as mused by three of the participants:

"...you just have to maneuver your way just to continue exposing the truth in your story despite disinformation." ^(P2)

"I make an effort to alert my immediate circle about the falsehood of the information and discourage them from sharing this kind of content." ^(P3)

"...you should always keep in mind that your main purpose is to deliver the right information... deliver the correct information." ^(P7)

Furthermore, for every cover that a journalist does, there is an underlying motive that each story they do is a proper perspective of the story that a journalist believes should be shared with the world, as exemplified by one participant:

"I believe that everybody who aspires to be a journalist should consider sharing their perspective with others." ^(P4)

Ultimately, their devotion to their advocacy is a fundamental factor and weapon in the fight against disinformation. By being reminded of their responsibilities and galvanizing the public to aid them in pursuing accurate information, these journalists become more productive while thoroughly engaging with the public they serve. In this regard, advocacy devotion is similar to the theme of media obligation. The difference is that this theme involves some public participation in the journalistic process and advocacy.

In the realm of journalistic Determination, encompassing positivity emanation, boundary adaptation, and advocacy devotion, journalists exhibit a dedicated pursuit of truth and an unwavering commitment to their profession's core values amidst the challenges posed by disinformation. Journalists' positivity emanation reflects their shared conviction that journalism will always be necessary and their positive perspective for the future of their field. Some use misinformation-fueled pessimism as fuel for negativity, but others use it as inspiration to expose lies in the interest of the greater good. A crucial ability, boundary adaptation entails remaining professional, using diplomatic methods, and accommodating different viewpoints without inciting hostility. A journalist's ability to manage relationships and create a peaceful media environment is essential when dealing with misinformation. Journalists passionate about advocacy devotion beyond obstacles, aggressively raising public awareness and promoting the significant positive effects of truthful information on society. Their steadfast dedication is vital in the battle against misinformation, highlighting the significance of public involvement in the journalistic process.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the age of disinformation, the participants inevitably come across circumstances that force them to make certain adjustments in their personal and professional lives in terms of their communication and reporting, ethical considerations and obligations, and positive engagement and adaptation. The principal aim of this study was to bring to light the unveiled experiences of journalists battling the impacts of disinformation. The participants shared many insights, modifications, and changes throughout the process. Hence, they have highlighted the following aspects:

Journalistic Operation

Even with widespread disinformation, producing a factual story is easier for the journalistic profession. Journalists play a crucial role when arranging their ideas and presenting the facts of what occurred through laborious data collection and in-depth research. There are three factors to consider when confirming their facts and dissecting the news's veracity.

The articulation of knowledge claims, the methods by which journalists substantiate such claims, and the justifications behind knowledge claims (Ekström et al., 2021).

Informative precision is the portion where journalists can present the gathered facts of a story impartially to the public. Most events are disseminated via various channels, written, or spoken, and managed by businesses or independent writers. Depending on the method of these platforms, it will have different impacts on the public due to how they distribute the content (Cavaliere, 2021). In disinformation, the impact is negative, as it is a strategic manipulation of information to mislead a person, social group, organization, or country (Arce, 2024). With the Internet harboring disinformation while simultaneously harboring the sources needed by journalists to determine if the data is accurate or not precisely, it is a journalist's inherent rule to fact-check all of their sources before, by the time of reporting, saying that what they wrote about the event is nothing but true.

However, there are cases where urgency overrides factuality. From the experience of one of the interviewees, the art of waiting to confirm their sources is often overlooked due to the fast-paced nature of the news industry and its motto to always get the first report on a story. Given the field's speed, journalists may need proper fact-checking to publish data content (Himma-Kadakas & Ojamets, 2022). With the Internet rampant with disinformation and combating it simultaneously, journalists look for ways to verify their sources, seeing these services as potentially helpful and reluctant to trust a single service for the truth (Brandtzaeg et al., 2017). However, it only partially depends on how many sources a journalist has. Suppose there needs to be more deliberate practice of precision. In that case, it allows disinformation to be disseminated to the public, giving them the wrong ideas that could harm them or those around them.

Journalism is only possible with the adamant practice of communication. As previously discussed, a journalist's relationship with his/her family, friends, and colleagues is significant when sharing and receiving news. Primarily, journalists engage with their audience via their reports. After debating with their colleagues about the factuality of the piece, the broadcast media builds a reputation for accurate and reliable reporting. That built reputation between the journalist and audience consequently impacts the evaluation of the news, which is the relational Trust that can arise from those reports that can be critical in the overall development of Trust in the journalism industry (Koliska et al., 2023).

However, it must be stated that not all communication done in relationships is to maintain it; it is also capable of breaking it. Due to disinformation combined with the behavior of social media users to comply without questioning claims, any person can pose to say something incorrect and spread it as accurate. Today's professional news offerings across all media can expand citizens' choices, information, engagement, and understanding, but they can also be confusing, disorientating, and even upsetting (Beckett & Deuze, 2016). As conducted through the interview, the audience is not the only relationship journalists have that can affect their work field. Disorientation can and has created fractures in their personal lives, but there is an understanding in their personal lives that these relationships continue to act as support systems.

Nevertheless, some difficulties prevail, pre- and post-writing each news report, that takes a toll on the journalist. The rising complications of oral or non-oral disinformation bring challenges too much to handle. Fighting disinformation means journalists must debunk incorrect news, which those who share it do not receive well. Those spreading the wrong information will continue to push that their side is the truth, that the interviewed journalists experience burning out. Due to the difficulties that disinformation creates, journalists feel frustrated with the perception of their increased affective labor due to there being more sources to check if they are factual or not, dissatisfaction with communication environments on particular social media platforms, and increased anxiety about the possible impact of social media use on both their professional reputations and personal well-being (Bossio & Holton, 2019).

However, journalists do not back down. Their passion for getting the truth out to the masses triumphs over any incorrect information spread by deceiving people who only want to get support for their benefit. In this case, passion is the pleasure of an interest, activity, or emotional engagement in journalistic work that encompasses enthusiasm, enjoyment, interest, fun, and satisfaction (Lindén, 2021). Though a journalistic project does not carry any emotion in its delivery due to its practice of being impartial, a person can recognize that specific projects are written out of passion through the research of the journalist behind them. Referring to such an emotion has thus been established as interference with the idealized processes of citizens becoming informed rather than "touched by" the news (Pajnik, 2024). However, the passion for reporting an actual event with all the accurate facts can influence the masses to better understand the realities in their community.

The journalistic process will always be due to its facts, and there is no writing or reporting around it with falsehood. There is a passion for putting the truth out there for the world to listen to, even with or without the combat against disinformation. Journalism does not occur in isolation because it is always surrounded by a community that will be impacted. It is surrounded by journalists who spend their time and effort validating their sources via thorough research in the media, communication in their relationships, and sharing in the community they write for. Journalists hold an intrinsic motivation that prevails over public service ones (Jackson et al., 2019), which is why the fight against disinformation is never a losing battle; journalism pushes through these challenges because journalists fight for the truth.

Producing accurate and factual stories remains an arduous task in the intricate realm of journalism, even without widespread disinformation. Journalists play a crucial role in meticulously organizing ideas, conducting extensive data collection, and engaging in thorough research to present reliable information. The meticulous process involves articulating knowledge claims, substantiating them through specific methods, and justifying these claims. These three critical factors underscore the rigorous nature of the undertaking.

Amidst the ever-evolving landscape of media channels, journalists face the challenge of navigating the impact of disinformation on their fact-checking efforts. The urgency to deliver news sometimes takes precedence over ensuring accuracy, which poses a risk of disseminating unchecked information, particularly in the fast-paced news industry. However, despite these challenges, effective communication remains the lifeblood of journalism, shaping relationships with audiences, colleagues, and societal systems.

The development of relational Trust is of utmost importance in the journalism industry, and it is built through accurate and reliable reporting. This Trust serves as a cornerstone for fostering Trust within the industry. While introducing disinformation brings complexities that can lead to burnout, frustration, and increased emotional labor, journalists resiliently persevere. Their unwavering passion for truth demonstrated through their emotional engagement in their work, becomes a driving force that triumphs over the obstacles posed by deceptive information.

Journalism, firmly anchored in the commitment to factual reporting, operates within a community where journalists validate sources, communicate effectively, and share their findings. The intrinsic motivation to serve the public emphasizes that the fight against disinformation is an ongoing battle, with journalists steadfastly pushing through challenges in their unwavering pursuit of truth.

Journalistic Introspection

Journalistic Introspection refers to internal reflection on duties, principles, and awareness of journalists' influence. Journalists should deliver precise and factual information to the public so that the public can make informed decisions. Thus, journalistic legitimacy can be gained through fulfilling the public's need for accurate and balanced information (Balod & Hameleers, 2021).

Media obligation is a cornerstone of ethics in journalism that deals with the journalists' role as a central figure in delivering factual information to the public. They are responsible for educating and galvanizing public sentiment to significantly influence politicians, business executives, and other decision-makers, compelling them to noticeably improve and, ultimately, resolve the issue at hand (Mathewson, 2021). However, this role has quickly become more challenging in the disinformation age. Due to the convenience and large Internet user base, the speed and volume of incorrect information transmitted by social media and other means on the Internet has become unprecedented (Schriffirin, 2017). In this regard, their obligation to deliver factual information for improvement and resolution is jeopardized as the public may be acting on incorrect information disseminated through the Internet.

However, some journalists have lost this obligation as they have failed to gain the public's Trust. Journalists frequently need to acknowledge their influence over the general population, leading to a lack of appropriate care and respect towards the public (Fink, 2018). For some news organizations, journalistic integrity takes second place to traffic on their articles with a profit-driven motive. Sensationalized coverage and 'clickbait' are becoming increasingly common in this digital media landscape. Ironically, journalists become sources of disinformation and misinformation. By doing so, they still need to deliver reliable, balanced, and accurate news and information for the public to act on.

With such a looming threat to the public's perceptions of journalists, upholding ethical standards and considerations is significant to delivering on their obligations to the public. Gathering and confirming facts is the first step towards ethical journalism. Journalists then attempt to present an impartial and trustworthy interpretation of the facts, which will remain open to further investigation. Journalists ought to provide transparency about their sources and procedures so that readers can evaluate the content themselves (Martono, 2017). Journalists cannot report and disseminate the absolute truth, but they provide the necessary, accurate, and balanced information to the public to make an informed judgment. In light of this, transparency of sources and processes significantly shapes public Trust in the field.

On the contrary, the application of ethical practices has proven difficult nowadays. Core ethical concepts in journalism, such as fairness, balance, and accuracy, are under pressure from internal policies that promote using multiple platforms to publish and broadcast news quickly and from the speed at which it is disseminated (Chavez & Freedman, 2022). As such, journalists often forego these ethical practices and considerations to meet deadlines and keep the freshness of the news. This shift fundamentally alters how journalists write news; gaps in ethical considerations could be sources of false information within the text.

Contrary to this view of a fixed truth is the ethical value of cosmopolitanism. Journalism should reflect and replicate the existing social norms and be receptive to different interpretations (Kim, 2017). When the journalist delivers factual information to the public, the public interprets this information, and during the process of interpretation, the line between facts and norms becomes blurred. In essence, the readers' interpretations and social realities are involved in the coverage of events. Thus, journalists must also consider various socio-cultural aspects influencing readers' interpretation to deliver their information effectively.

Ethical considerations coincide with journalists acknowledging their influence on various aspects of societal life and using that influence carefully. It is crucial for journalists to effectively deliver their information as this information is influential in shaping the socio-political lives of individuals. For a considerable amount of time, print journalism has been regarded as a crucial institution in democratic politics, as it improves transparency, offers a platform for discussion, and encourages public involvement (Hallin & Mellado, 2017). In this sense, journalism's role in checking established powers and probing into establishments is a condition for functioning democracies (Márquez-Ramírez et al., 2020). Journalists must be aware of their influence in these critical aspects of discourse, as their work is the platform from which public discourse is facilitated. In that regard, combatting disinformation is essential to allow public discourse to flourish properly through balanced information.

However, journalists' roles in undemocratic societies are different. The diversity of political cultures and socio-cultural value systems worldwide must be considered by the catalogs of media functions and services currently available for political life (Hanitzsch & Vost, 2018). The state controls the media in these undemocratic societies, and journalistic autonomy is not exercised. In doing so, the media fails to be the 'watchdogs' of the state and embellishes or outright omits any information that tarnishes the image of the state. Thus, journalists' influence in socio-political life in these societies is minimized, forcing them to report on false narratives.

In summary, contemporary journalism faces a critical crossroads where ethical responsibilities collide with the difficulties of disinformation and the ever-changing media landscape. The foundation of journalistic credibility lies in the accurate dissemination of information, meeting the public's need for accuracy. However, the Internet's unparalleled spread of misinformation complicates the role of journalists as educators and influencers in socio-political affairs. Ethical considerations, crucial for maintaining journalistic integrity, encounter obstacles as the demands of speed and platforms often lead to compromises regarding fairness, balance, and accuracy. Despite these challenges, the ethical principle of cosmopolitanism encourages journalists to be open to diverse interpretations influenced by socio-cultural factors. Journalists, fully aware of their influential position, must navigate carefully in shaping socio-political discourse. In democratic societies, journalism plays a vital role as an institution that supports transparency, discussion, and public engagement, making it imperative to combat disinformation to preserve the health of democracy. Conversely, in undemocratic societies, limited journalistic autonomy hinders the media's role as a tool of the state, minimizing the influence of journalists and perpetuating false narratives. Amidst these challenges, the call for ethical considerations and the fight against disinformation remains crucial in safeguarding the essential functions of journalism in diverse societal contexts.

Journalistic Determination

Navigating the field of journalism demands a nuanced response to the challenges of disinformation. Journalists, as the vanguards of truth, exhibit a remarkable ability to positively engage with their profession while adapting to the evolving dynamics of information dissemination. Many journalists underscore the importance of maintaining a commitment to excellence as a pivotal response to disinformation (Tenove & MacLellan, 2021).

Positivity Emanation, emerging as a guiding ethos that motivates journalists to uphold their fundamental values, is further reinforced by the evolving outlook of fact-checking journalism. Shaped as a new practice to combat disinformation or as an emerging journalistic genre, fact-checking has become an integral part of the optimistic stance adopted by journalists (Graves, 2016). This inherent resilience displayed by journalists is not just a reactive response to

challenges but a proactive commitment to addressing the complexities introduced by technological advancements and changing behaviors of individuals.

Critics contend that an overemphasis on debunking disinformation could inadvertently contribute to a sense of dismay among media professionals (Kvetanová et al., 2020). In this view, journalists might become deeply rooted in a defensive position, combating disinformation rather than actively shaping a positive narrative about the enduring impact of journalism. However, encouraging a passion for truth is not just about distinguishing between accurate and misleading information but instilling a profound appreciation for the pursuit of truth. This intrinsic value that binds journalists together also resonates as a vital aspect of positive engagement and adaptation in the ever-evolving landscape of journalism (Rodríguez-Pérez et al., 2021).

The skill of maintaining professionalism while employing diplomatic approaches becomes essential when it comes to facing the dilemmas of disinformation. Boundary adaptation extends beyond reporting facts to engage with the evolving dynamics of public opinion. The iterative process of editorial fact-checking contributes to accuracy and enhances the overall quality of storytelling (Damasceno & Patrício, 2020). This collaborative approach in the editing process emphasizes the democratic underpinnings of journalism, recognizing that diverse perspectives enhance the overall quality of a piece by exposing blind spots and biases. Professional journalists engage in 'collective efforts to set up boundaries to exercise jurisdictional control (Serban, 2019). Furthermore, it is essential for the professionalization of journalism as it underscores how journalists delineate their working conditions and practices within the broader social context of disinformation. While journalism serves as a bridge connecting individuals with society, it consistently grapples with the challenge of setting itself apart, constructing a professional habit that enables it to coexist with other fields while accentuating its distinctiveness.

However, news leaders' concerns about journalists' skills highlight potential gaps in their ability to counter false information effectively (DeCillia & Clark, 2023). As journalism evolves in the digital age, the field demands professional adaptability. The increasing emphasis on fact-checking, while contributing to the accuracy of information, raises questions about the preparedness of journalists to manage the complexities of the media environment. By actively rebutting false information, this engagement reinforces their ability to navigate perspectives and contribute to a more informed public discourse by showcasing the adaptability required in the face of evolving challenges to uphold journalistic integrity.

Advocacy devotion surfaces as a formidable driving factor propelling journalists in their mission to counter disinformation. This steadfast commitment goes beyond the routine dissemination of facts; journalists proactively cultivate public awareness and advocate for accurate information's far-reaching influence on society. In line with broader industry challenges, journalists grapple with complex decisions on how to respond to disinformation. The core belief shared among journalists is that their primary purpose is to deliver the proper and correct information, instilling a sense of responsibility (Egelhofer, 2019). It signifies their recognition of the indispensable role that accurate information plays in shaping the narrative of society.

Despite this, it is viewed skeptically by some who argue that journalists should maintain a neutral stance and refrain from actively engaging in advocacy (Višňovský & Radošinská, 2021). It may compromise journalistic objectivity and fuel perceptions of bias instead of actively promoting specific viewpoints. This perspective suggests that journalists, in their pursuit of accuracy, should avoid crossing into the realm of advocacy to prevent potential polarization and to maintain the credibility of their reporting. Moreover, there is a need to reintroduce truth-finding procedures that possess a collective binding force, avoiding the division of society into distinct trust communities associated with various media types (Michailidou & Trenz, 2021). This approach emphasizes the importance of adapting journalistic practices to foster a shared commitment to truth that unites rather than segregates communities based on their media preferences. Journalists' primary responsibility is delivering information without promoting a particular narrative or viewpoint. It represents an authentic expression by journalists to expose the truth and correct false or dubious statements present in the public domain (DeCillia & Clark, 2023).

Thus, in journalism, the challenges presented by disinformation have prompted journalists to respond proactively and flexibly. Guided by the principle of emanating positivity, journalists are committed to upholding core values and navigating the complexities introduced by technological advancements. Fact-checking journalism has emerged as a vital practice, not only to combat disinformation but also as a testament to the resilience and optimism of journalists. The iterative process of editorial fact-checking goes beyond ensuring accuracy, aiming to enhance the overall quality of storytelling and uphold democratic values within journalism. While concerns persist regarding journalists' skills and potential gaps in countering false information, their unwavering commitment to advocacy remains steadfast. This

dedication extends beyond mere dissemination of facts, as journalists actively cultivate public awareness and advocate for accurate information's profound impact on society. However, skepticism arises regarding the advocacy stance, as some argue for journalistic neutrality to prevent the perception of bias and maintain credibility. Despite these debates, a shared commitment to truth remains central, emphasizing the necessity for journalistic practices that unite rather than divide communities based on media preferences. In navigating these dilemmas, maintaining professionalism, adapting to evolving public opinion dynamics, and preserving journalistic integrity become crucial aspects of journalists' dedication to delivering accurate information while shaping a positive narrative about the enduring impact of journalism.

V. CONCLUSION

This phenomenological study investigates journalists' experiences surrounding disinformation. Disinformation is a social phenomenon in which false information is deliberately spread throughout vast channels to fulfill agendas. Journalists face many challenges, including skepticism of their work, public perception of their profession, burnout, stress, and ensuring an accurate and balanced delivery of the information they report. The analysis of this study used a qualitative data-gathering approach, which was achieved by conducting interviews with relevant participants.

In this study, journalists from media organizations and institutions in Qatar were chosen to highlight their lived experiences and perceptions, specifically from their personal and professional lives. These journalists are at the forefront of combating disinformation, but their personal lives interplay with their professional lives to the point that journalists deal with this differently.

The study highlights the multifaceted nature of journalistic operations in combating disinformation and navigating the complexities of the modern media landscape. Journalists are depicted as engaging in systematic approaches to gathering and scrutinizing information, maintaining ethical standards, and fulfilling their obligations to the public. Despite the prevalence of disinformation, journalists demonstrate optimism and Determination, foreseeing a brighter future where a more empowered and critical public seeks truth.

Furthermore, the study delves into journalists' personal and professional experiences, highlighting the challenges they face and the values they uphold. It identifies three central themes—Journalistic Operation, Journalistic Introspection, and Journalistic Determination—and explores how these themes intersect in journalists' lives. The findings emphasize the difficulties of producing accurate stories amidst the ever-changing media landscape and the importance of trust-building and effective communication in journalism.

Ethical considerations are paramount in this context, particularly in disinformation and the pressure for immediacy. The text underscores the ethical obligations of journalists in fulfilling the public's demand for precise and impartial information despite challenges posed by disinformation on the Internet. It also touches upon the role of journalism in democratic societies, where the fight against disinformation is crucial for safeguarding democracy, contrasting with undemocratic societies where limited journalistic autonomy perpetuates false narratives.

This study recommends that future researchers interested in knowing the lived experiences of journalists in the age of disinformation in Qatar study how journalists adapt to the evolving dynamics of media platforms, especially in the digital age. Future researchers must explore the challenges and opportunities presented by different channels and assess the impact on the quality of journalism, ethical considerations, and overall public perception.

This research provided a large body of data and outcomes, yet the study has more room for further investigation in future research studies. Although the journalists came from differing nationalities, there could be bias as most journalists are from the same nationality. This perceived bias has been causing limitations regarding the containment of disinformation within a Qatari context. The researchers also found that the platform used to conduct the participants' online interviews needed to be improved. An online interview does not reflect the participants' experiences and adjustments conveyed through their nonverbal cues. The researchers advised that future investigations on journalists must have a sample size that includes a broader variety of nationalities to capture the global nature of disinformation. Additionally, the variety of the participants' nationalities ensures a higher level of data dependability and a more precise comparative analysis by gathering more responses from individuals of various backgrounds.

Further improvements can be implemented to capture the essence of journalistic roles across nations with a free and independent press or a press that the government controls. Future researchers may widen their understanding of the journalists' adaptation by investigating the influence of passion and emotional engagement in journalistic work. Understanding how these factors contribute to the resilience of journalists in the face of disinformation and exploring their impact on the delivery of accurate and reliable information is crucial in perceiving the journalists' expression of themselves in their writing. Other researchers can evaluate the efficacy of fact-checking practices in journalism and

examine how well these journalists adjust their methodology to meet the challenge of disinformation. This study's investigation was done as an integration to other adjustments. The researchers believe that evaluating their fact-checking processes is critical in understanding journalists' methods and processes in the disinformation age.

Moreover, future researchers may also be able to broaden their scope of study to include the phenomenon of misinformation and their experiences regarding the public's media and information literacy. This could provide a more holistic view of the adjustments the journalists made to combat disinformation. This expansion of the scope allows future researchers to have a more nuanced and detailed analysis of rampant disinformation and extract more themes on this topic.

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